

Features of Retinal Microcirculation in Hypertensive Retinopathy: The Influence of Endothelial Dysfunction

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Abstract: *Endothelial monocyte-activating peptide-II levels in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension*

Objective: *To determine the level of endothelial monocyte-activating peptide-II (EMAP-II) in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM1) with microangiopathy as a marker of endothelial dysfunction, to study the effect of arterial hypertension on the level of this factor, as well as its relationship with dilation and other risk factors.*

Materials and methods. *The study included 23 patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension, 10 patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy without hypertension, and 28 healthy controls. EMAP-II levels were determined by enzyme immunoassay. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, and regression analysis.*

Results. *EMAP-II levels were found to be increased in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension compared to the control group (5.23 ± 1.66 ng/ml and 1.25 ± 0.76 ng/ml, respectively, $p < 0.01$), as well as in patients with type 1 hypertension and without arterial hypertension (5.3 ± 1.66 ng/ml and 3.63 ± 1.9 , respectively, $p < 0.01$). EMAP-II levels were directly correlated with the main indicators of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism and inversely correlated with the index of endothelium-dependent dilation ($p < 0.05$).*

Conclusion: *Type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension is accompanied by an increase in serum EMAP-II content, which may be a manifestation of endothelial dysfunction. Arterial hypertension, hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia may affect the increase in EMAP-II.*

Key words: *endothelial monocyte-activating peptide, endothelial dysfunction, diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension.*

Introduction:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) and arterial hypertension are diseases of great social importance, the prevalence of which is steadily increasing worldwide [1]. Cardiovascular diseases are the main cause of death in diabetes [2]. In addition, diabetes increases the risk of developing arterial hypertension, which, in turn, is a leading risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. On the other hand, arterial hypertension, accompanied by the formation of insulin resistance, is associated with a higher risk of developing metabolic complications compared to people with normal blood pressure and may precede the development of diabetes [1]. The combination of diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension significantly affects the prognosis of cardiovascular pathology, the ability to achieve targeted compensation of carbohydrate metabolism and blood pressure, and contributes to the acceleration of damage to the heart, blood vessels and kidneys, which subsequently leads to the development of catastrophes.

Endothelial dysfunction is an early and important step in the development of diabetic angiopathies [4]. The functional state of the endothelium is characterized, on the one hand, by endothelium-dependent dilation and, on the other hand, by the content of endothelial vasoactive factors.

Endothelial monocyte-activating peptide-II (EMAP-II) is a multifunctional polypeptide with anti-inflammatory and antiangiogenesis activities [5].

Atherosclerotic changes in the vascular wall have been shown to occur long before clinical symptoms appear [6]. Many studies have shown that the atherosclerotic process begins already in adolescence and its development is determined by the same factors as in adults [7]. Prospective studies have shown an association between traditional risk factors for cardiovascular disease in healthy children and atherosclerotic lesions of the carotid arteries in adults [8].

EMAP-II levels may be a marker of endothelial activation and dysfunction in both type 1 diabetes (T1DM) and hypertension. However, there are no studies in the scientific literature that have examined serum EMAP-II levels in type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and hypertension, as well as their association with other cardiovascular risk factors in this pathological condition.

Purpose

The aim of our study was to determine the level of EMAP-II as a marker of endothelial dysfunction in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy, to study the effect of arterial hypertension on the level of this factor, as well as its relationship with indicators of endothelium-dependent dilation, as well as other risk factors for the development of cardiovascular pathology.

Materials and methods

The study involved 58 subjects. Among them were 28 healthy controls and 33 patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy, who were divided as follows: 23 patients with arterial hypertension and 10 patients with normal blood pressure. The groups were matched for age and sex. The clinical and laboratory characteristics of the subjects are presented in Table 1. Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

Arterial hypertension was diagnosed when blood pressure was higher than 140/90 mm Hg. or when taking antihypertensive drugs [9]. All patients with arterial hypertension had stage 2 disease. According to the classification of arterial hypertension according to blood pressure, stage 1 was recorded in 9 (39.13%) patients, and stage 2 in 14 (60.86%) patients. The average systolic blood pressure was 162.17 ± 12.95 mm Hg, and diastolic blood pressure was 100.87 ± 5.36 mm Hg. In the group of patients with arterial hypertension, 12 (52.17%) patients received antihypertensive drugs: 3 (13.04%) patients - beta-blockers, 4 (17.39%) - diuretics (indapamide), 2 (8.69%) - a combination of beta-blockers and indapamide (% 13, moxonide, 0.3). 11 (47.82%) patients did not receive antihypertensive therapy.

None of the subjects studied were following a hypolipidemic diet or taking medications to correct dyslipidemia.

When examining the fundus of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with arterial hypertension, 12 (52.17%) of them had proliferative retinopathy, 7 (30.43%) had preproliferative retinopathy, 3 (13.04%) had nonproliferative retinopathy, and 1 (4.34%) had diabetic retinopathy. Porta M.) [10]. In the group of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with normal blood pressure, proliferative retinopathy was detected in 3 (30%), preproliferative retinopathy in 1 (10%), nonproliferative retinopathy in 4 (40%) patients, and diabetic retinal angiopathy in 2 (20%) patients.

Stage IV diabetic nephropathy, the stage of proteinuria, was detected in 23 (100%) patients with type 1 diabetes with arterial hypertension, in 5 (50%) patients in the non-hypertensive group. In 5 patients without hypertension (50%), stage III diabetic nephropathy and microalbuminuria (according to the Mogensen CE, 1983 classification) were observed [11].

Endothelium-dependent vasodilation was measured using the standard Zellemeier technique [12].

The level of EMAP-II was determined by enzyme immunoassay using Ampr sorption columns (Amersham Life science) and Amersham Pharmabiotech (England) test systems. The studies were conducted on a StatFax-303 Plus (USA) plate ELISA analyzer.

Statistical processing of data was carried out using the standard statistical package of Microsoft Excel using transformation and descriptive statistics methods. The reliability of differences in mean values was determined using the Student t-test. The difference was considered significant at a p value of <0.05 . Correlation analysis was performed using the Pearson coefficient. The results obtained were also analyzed using multiple regression correlation analysis.

The research protocol was approved by the Medical Ethics Committee of the Khmelnytsky Regional Hospital (Minutes No. 5 dated October 5, 2003).

Results

As a result of our study, it was found that the level of EMAP-II in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension was 5.23 ± 1.66 ng/ml; in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy without hypertension - 3.63 ± 1.9 ng/ml, in the serum of control individuals - 1.25 ± 0.76 ng/ml (Fig. 1).

The highest levels of EMAP-II were observed in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes, who also had microangiopathy and arterial hypertension.

When analyzing the obtained data, we found a statistically significant increase in the content of EMAP-II in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension by 4.18 times ($p < 0.01$) compared to the corresponding indicator in the control group.

A significant increase in EMAP-II of 2.9-fold ($p < 0.01$) was observed in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with non-hypertensive microangiopathy compared to the control group.

In patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension, the level of the studied cytokine was significantly higher than in patients with normal blood pressure - 1.44 times ($p = 0.01$).

Thus, the amount of EMAP-II in the blood was significantly higher in the group of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension compared to both the control group and the non-hypertensive group.

As a result of the study of endothelium-dependent vasodilation, it was found that in patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension, its level was $2.73 \pm 1.99\%$; in patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy without hypertension - $3.44 \pm 1.31\%$, and in control subjects - $8.4 \pm 4.08\%$. Thus, in the group of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension, endothelium-dependent dilation was weakened both in comparison with the indicator in the control group and in comparison with the group without hypertension.

When conducting a correlation analysis, a statistically significant inverse correlation was found between the content of EMAP-II in serum and an indicator characterizing endothelium-dependent dilation, both in the group of patients with diabetes and arterial hypertension, and in people with normal blood pressure.

A direct correlation was found between glycated hemoglobin, glucose, and serum EMAP-II levels in diabetic patients in both groups.

Since lipid metabolism disorders were detected in the individuals examined during our study, it was interesting to know the effect of dyslipidemia on the increase in EMAP-II levels in patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy, who had arterial hypertension and normal blood pressure.

A direct correlation was found between the levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoproteins in the serum of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and the level of EMAP-II, both in the group with and without arterial hypertension.

Serum EMAP-II levels in both groups of type 1 diabetic patients were inversely correlated with high-density lipoprotein content.

We performed multivariate regression analysis to determine the relationship between EMAP-II levels and traditional risk factors for cardiovascular pathology in a group of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathies.

Thus, when conducting multivariate regression analysis, the statistically significant indicators affecting the level of EMAP-II in the blood in the group of patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension were glycated hemoglobin, total cholesterol and triglycerides in the blood serum, and in the blood serum - only in patients with normal hemoglobin levels.

Correlation and regression analysis revealed a relationship between systolic and diastolic blood pressure and EMAP-II in the serum of patients with arterial hypertension (Figure 2).

Discussion

As a result of the study, we found that the serum level of EMAP-II in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy and arterial hypertension was increased both in the control group and in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with microangiopathy without hypertension, which may be a manifestation of endothelial activation, as this is a violation of arterial hypertension and the possible

effect of hypertension on s. In turn, endothelial dysfunction may serve as a prerequisite for the development of atherosclerosis in these patients, despite their young age.

Many studies have shown that in cardiovascular diseases, namely arterial hypertension, coronary heart disease, circulatory failure, the release of pro-inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein, interleukins-1 and -6 [13], adhesion molecules increase, which, in turn, is associated with an increased risk of developing arterial hypertension [14].

Changes in the concentration of circulating endothelial products may indicate endothelial activation and dysfunction at a preclinical stage [15].

EMAP-II has a strong effect on endothelial cells. It is able to regulate the procoagulant functions of the latter, and also has a chemotactic effect on monocytes and granulocytes [16]. In endothelial cells, EMAP-II enhances the expression of E- and P-selectin, the secretion of von Willebrand factor, and the production of tumor necrosis factor [2]. EMAP-II induces apoptosis of endothelial cells, inhibits proliferation, vascularization, and neoangiogenesis. This contributes to the disruption of the functional state of the endothelium.

Therefore, the increased EMAP-II levels detected in our study in patients with type 1 diabetes combined with arterial hypertension may be a manifestation of endothelial dysfunction and activation in these pathological conditions, which is also confirmed by the observed inverse correlation between EMAP-II levels and the severity of endothelium-dependent diabetes mellitus.

It should also be noted that when conducting correlation-regression analysis, systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels were independent reliable factors leading to an increase in serum EMAP-II levels, which, in our opinion, once again emphasizes the importance of arterial hypertension in patients with endothelial dysfunction in type 1 diabetes.

The increased content of EMAP-II in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus with non-hypertensive microangiopathy compared with the control group may also indicate the role of hyperglycemia in the development of these diseases. These assumptions are also supported by the data of correlation analysis, which revealed a direct relationship between glycated hemoglobin, blood glucose levels on the one hand, and the content of EMAP-II in serum on the other.

When conducting multivariate regression analysis, the level of glycated hemoglobin was an independent reliable factor leading to an increase in serum EMAP-II levels, which, in our opinion, once again emphasizes the importance of hyperglycemia in the development of endothelial dysfunction in patients with type 1 diabetes, as well as arterial hypertension with microangiopathy.

We previously obtained similar results when studying serum EMAP-II levels in patients with type 2 DM [17], as well as in children and adolescents with DM [18].

Lipid metabolism disorders play an important role in the initiation and progression of atherosclerosis, as well as in the development of endothelial dysfunction [19]. Increased serum EMAP-II levels in the studied individuals may be associated with dyslipidemia. Changes in the lipid spectrum were observed in patients with arterial hypertension and normal blood pressure.

Our correlation analysis confirms these assumptions and demonstrates the influence of dyslipidemia on the increase in serum EMAP-II content in patients with type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy, both with and without arterial hypertension.

Conclusion

Type 1 diabetes with microangiopathy, both with arterial hypertension and with normal arterial pressure, is accompanied by an increase in the content of EMAP-II in the blood serum.

An increase in the content of EMAP-II in the blood serum may be one of the manifestations of endothelial activation, which contributes to the development of atherosclerotic changes in patients with this pathology, despite their young age.

Arterial hypertension, hyperglycemia, and dyslipidemia may contribute to increased serum EMAP-II levels.

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